

MARKETING OF ECOLOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES AND SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: TRAINING OF EXPERTS FOR THE EFFECTIVE PROMOTION OF “GREEN” PRODUCTS

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Abstract: In the context of global environmental problems and sustainable development, the marketing of ecological technologies and products is becoming an important tool for bringing "green" technologies to market. This approach focuses on the creation and implementation of environmentally friendly and energy-efficient products that help reduce negative environmental impacts. It is important to understand the needs of the target audience and create communications that highlight the environmental benefits of products. Training specialists in this field requires knowledge of sustainable development, ecology, marketing, and innovative technologies.

Keywords: marketing, environmental technologies, sustainable development, "green" products, ecology, marketing strategies, environmentally friendly products, promotion, innovation.

Xülasə: Qlobal ekoloji problemlər və davamlı inkişaf kontekstində ekoloji texnologiyaların və məhsulların marketinqi “yaşıl” texnologiyaların bazara çıxarılması üçün mühüm vasitəyə çevrilir. Bu yanaşma ətraf mühitə mənfi təsirləri azaltmağa kömək edən ekoloji cəhətdən təmiz və enerjiliyə qənaət edən məhsulların yaradılmasına və həyata keçirilməsinə yönəlib. Hədəf auditoriyasının ehtiyaclarını anlamaq və məhsulların ekoloji faydalarını vurğulayan kommunikasiyalar qurmaq vacibdir. Bu sahədə mütəxəssislərin hazırlanması davamlı inkişaf, ekologiya, marketinq və innovativ texnologiyalar sahəsində bilik tələb edir.

Açar sözlər: marketinq, ekoloji texnologiyalar, davamlı inkişaf, “yaşıl” məhsullar, ekologiya, marketinq strategiyaları, ekoloji cəhətdən təmiz məhsullar, təşviq, innovasiya.

Today's environmental challenges, such as climate change, natural resource depletion, and pollution, require businesses and societies to adopt environmentally friendly technologies and solutions. In these circumstances, marketing environmental technologies and sustainable development is becoming an important tool in promoting "green" products. However, effectively promoting environmentally friendly products and services requires experts who understand both environmental and marketing aspects. This article examines the fundamental elements of marketing environmental technologies and the need to train qualified experts who can effectively promote these products. Green marketing is the process of developing and implementing marketing strategies aimed at promoting products and technologies that minimize negative environmental impact. The evolution of marketing in

the context of sustainable development represents a shift from traditional consumer marketing to marketing focused on environmental values and sustainable consumption. (Kotler & Armstrong, 2017).

The elements of green marketing are as follows:

1. A product is a good or service designed with environmental considerations in mind, from using recycled materials to minimizing carbon footprint. (Peattie & Crane, 2005)
2. Price – Green products often command a higher price due to the use of more expensive technology and materials, but the price can also reflect long-term savings for the consumer. ☐ (Belz & Peattie, 2009).
3. Place – Promotion of environmentally friendly products should be achieved through channels that support sustainable practices (e.g., eco-stores or online platforms). (Kotler & Armstrong, 2017)
4. Promotion – use a variety of communication channels, including digital marketing, social media, PR campaigns, and educational initiatives, to convey the product's value to consumers. (Peattie & Crane, 2005).

Successful examples of green marketing strategies include brands like **IKEA**, which extensively uses recycled materials, and **Patagonia**, which reaches new consumers through environmental responsibility and sustainable production. (Belz & Peattie, 2009) Consumer interest in environmentally friendly and sustainable products is growing every year. The effects of climate change and environmental disasters are increasingly affecting public awareness, increasing the demand for such goods and services. For example, interest in environmentally friendly products that minimize environmental impact is increasing in the wake of major natural disasters such as hurricanes and floods. (O'Rourke, 2003). However, with the growing interest in environmentally friendly products comes the problem of **greenwashing**, a marketing strategy where companies claim their products are environmentally friendly when in fact they are not. (Belz & Peattie, 2009) This erodes consumer trust and necessitates honest certifications and standards to prove product environmental friendliness. This highlights the need for innovative approaches to promote transparency and fairness in the market. (Schaltegger & Wagner, 2011). Sustainable consumers often base their decisions not only on price but also on their awareness of the sustainability impact of their purchases. This trend in consumer behavior has a significant impact on the marketing of green technologies.

To effectively promote “green” products, the psychographic and behavioral aspects of consumers must be considered:

1. The psychology of environmentally conscious consumers – Awareness of environmental issues motivates consumers to seek sustainable products. (O'Rourke, 2003).
2. Tools that encourage sustainable purchasing – Labels and certifications such as Fair Trade and Energy Star are becoming important indicators of product environmental friendliness. This helps

consumers make informed choices and support companies working with green technologies. (Schaltegger & Wagner, 2011).

The use of digital technologies, including social media and mobile applications, allows consumers to effectively inform consumers about the benefits of environmentally friendly products. (Elkington, 1999)

The market for organic products continues to grow, and companies need experts who can develop and implement strategies to promote such products. This requires training experts who combine knowledge in ecology and marketing. (Lozano, 2013)

The training of such experts should include the following core competencies:

- **Sustainability knowledge** – Understanding of environmental regulations, standards, and sustainable production principles.
- **Marketing strategy development skills** – the ability to adapt traditional marketing approaches to the characteristics of organic products. (Moser, 2017)
- **Digital skills** – the ability to use online channels and social media to promote products and work with big data to analyze consumer demand (Lozano, 2013)

Curriculum and specialized courses at universities and business schools play a crucial role in preparing staff for the green economy. Many universities are beginning to offer courses in sustainable business and green marketing, teaching students how to develop strategies to effectively market green technologies. (Kotler & Armstrong, 2017). Effectively promoting green products requires the use of innovative marketing methods that highlight the environmental benefits of products.

One such method is the use of digital technologies to communicate with consumers. Social media and online platforms allow companies to effectively communicate the benefits of their products, create educational campaigns, and engage consumers in active discussions about sustainable solutions. (Elkington, 1999). As an example of a successful campaign, **Tesla** is popularizing electric cars by promoting the idea that sustainable transportation is not only environmentally friendly but also beneficial for consumers. **IKEA** is also worth mentioning, as it actively incorporates recycled materials into its products and uses environmentally friendly technologies in its production processes. The development of the organic food market is not only a challenge but also a huge potential for businesses. Companies that invest in sustainable technologies and green production can not only save the environment but also attract new, environmentally conscious consumers. (Moser, 2017).

The successful introduction of green technologies requires highly qualified professionals who can effectively develop and implement marketing strategies for "green" products. Educational institutions play a crucial role in training such personnel by providing students with the knowledge and skills necessary to operate in a green economy. (Lozano, 2013).

References:

1. **Kotler, P., & Armstrong, G.** (2017). *Principles of Marketing*. Pearson Education.
2. **Peattie, K., & Crane, A.** (2005). Green marketing: Legend, myth, farce or prophesy? *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*.
3. **Belz, F.-M., & Peattie, K.** (2009). *Sustainability Marketing: A Global Perspective*. Wiley.
4. **O'Rourke, D.** (2003). Outsourcing regulation: Analyzing nongovernmental systems of labor and environmental governance. *The Policy Studies Journal*, 31(1), 1-29.
5. **Schaltegger, S., & Wagner, M.** (2011). Sustainable Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Innovation: Categories and Interactions. *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 20(4), 222-238.
6. **Lozano, R.** (2013). Are Companies Really Implementing Sustainable Practices? *Business Strategy and the Environment*, 22(1), 1-14.
7. **Elkington, J.** (1999). *Cannibals with Forks: The Triple Bottom Line of 21st Century Business*. New Society Publishers.
8. **Moser, R.** (2017). The Role of Marketing in the Transition to a Circular Economy. *Business and Politics*, 19(2), 207-226